

Studies on Some Soluble Palladium(II) Chelates in Aqueous Solution. Part IV. Composition and Stability of Palladium (II) Chelates of Alizarin Red S and Nitroso R-Salt

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The formation of coloured chelates of palladium (II) with sodium alizarin-3-sulphonate (Alizarin Red S) and with sodium 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate (Nitroso R-salt) has been described. The former is a 1:2 (Pd: ligand) chelate, has a red colour ($\lambda_{\max}$ 450 m μ) at pH 4.0, and is stable between pH 3.0 and 5.0. The apparent stability constant is $10^{8.9}$, as determined by two different methods.

The latter has a composition of 2Pd : 3Nitroso R-salt with a $\lambda_{\max}$ of 420 m μ at pH 3.0 and is stable at a wide range of pH (1.0 to 11.0). The positions of the chelate rings in both the chelates have been suggested.

Some new chromogenic ligands for bivalent palladium, forming coloured chelates, have already been reported¹⁻⁴. In the present communication two more chromogenic ligands, viz., sodium 1,2-dihydroxyanthraquinone-3-sulphonate (Alizarin Red S; abbr. ARS) and sodium 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate (Nitroso R-salt; abbr. NRS) have been studied and the compositions and other characteristics of the chelates described.

EXPERIMENTAL

Absorbance and pH measurements were carried out as described earlier⁴, using 1 cm thickness of the solutions. Solutions of ARS and NRS (B.D.H. reagents) were prepared by dissolving suitable amounts in water. Palladium chloride (Johnson, Matthey & Co) solution was prepared by dissolving in water and standardising it by precipitating with dimethylglyoxime.

Procedure.—Measurements were made at 25°. The methods for the determination of the compositions were (i) method of continued variations, (ii) mole-ratio method, and (iii) slope-ratio method.

Pd (II)-ARS Chelate

Palladium (II) with Alizarin Red S forms a soluble, red-coloured chelate. The colour intensity is stable with time, the absorbance of the mixtures undergoing no decrease on keeping for 48 hr. at the room temperature. The absorption curve of the chelate was obtained for the different ratios of palladium: ARS at pH 4.0. The absorption curve exhibits only one maximum at 450 m μ , showing the presence of only one complex under the

1. Sangal and Dey, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 464.
2. *Idem, ibid.*, 1964, 41, 306.
3. Munshi and Dey, *Talanta*, 1964, 11, 1165.
4. Seth and Dey, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 794.
5. Mukherji and Dey, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, 6, 314.
6. Yoo and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.

conditions employed. The $\lambda_{\max}$ of the reagent at the same pH was 420 m μ . The study was made at 490 and 500 m μ as at these wave lengths the reagent showed a small absorbance.

The ratio of palladium to ARS in the chelate was 1:2, as determined by the above mentioned methods.* The chelate is stable between pH 3.0 and 5.0 as shown by the constancy of the $\lambda_{\max}$ within this range (Fig. 2). The $\lambda_{\max}$ shifts to 540 m μ , which is the $\lambda_{\max}$ of the reagent alone above pH 5.0.

FIG. 1. By the method of continued variations.
 $p=1$; pH=4.0; $\mu=0.1M$ (NaClO₄).
 In curves A—C, $c=1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$, $5.0 \times 10^{-4}M$,
 and $2.5 \times 10^{-4}M$ respectively.

FIG. 2. Variation of $\lambda_{\max}$ with pH.
 $p=2$; $c=1.0 \times 10^{-4}M$.

The chelation may be suggested to occur between the quinoid oxygen and the α -phenolic oxygen, as indicated by the neutral nature of the chelate, ascertained by electrophoresis experiments as well as by its property of remaining unabsorbed by anionic or cationic ion-exchange resins.

Evaluation of Stability Constant.—The stability constant of the chelate was calculated as described earlier⁵, concentrations used being those in Fig. 1. The values of K are recorded in Table I.

* In the Figs. c represents the conc. of PdCl₂ and c' that of the ligand; $p=c'/c$.

TABLE I

Stability constant (log K) of Pd-NRS chelate.

Method employed.	pH.	Ionic strength (μ).	log K.	ΔG° at 25° (kcal.).
Dey <i>et al.</i>	4.0	0.1M (NaClO ₄)	8.9±0.2	-12.3±0.3
Mole-ratio.	4.0	0.1M (NaClO ₄)	8.9±0.1	-12.3±0.2

Palladium (II)-Nitroso R-salt Chelate

The absorption curves of mixtures with varying ratios of Pd:NRS at pH 4.0 revealed the formation of only one complex with a $\lambda_{\max}$ of 420 m μ ($\lambda_{\max}$ of the reagent is 370 m μ at pH 4.0). The colour intensity is stable even up to 72 hours at the room temperature.

The composition comes to be 2:3 (Pd: NRS) as is shown by the continued variations curve (Fig. 3) and mole-ratio curve (Fig. 4) and further supported by the slope-ratio curves (not shown).

FIG. 3. By the method of continued variations.
 $p = 1$; pH = 3.0; $\lambda_{\max} = 420$ m μ .
 In curves A—C, $c = 2.50 \times 10^{-4}M$, $1.67 \times 10^{-4}M$,
 and $1.25 \times 10^{-4}M$ respectively.

The $\lambda_{\max}$ of the chelate (420 m μ) holds good from pH 1.0 to 11.0, showing the stability of the complex formed within this range of pH, whereas the absorbance values remain constant between pH 3.0 and 7.5.

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FIG. 4. By the mole-ratio method (pH 3.0; $\lambda_{\max} = 420$ m μ).
 Conc. of NRS in A and B are $1.0 \times 10^{-4}M$
 and $0.67 \times 10^{-5}M$ respectively

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